

Studies in Some Mixed Ligand Complexes Containing β -Dicarbonyls. Part—IV. Complexes of Cu(II) with Salicylaldehyde and 2-OH-Acetophenone as Primary Ligands and Acetoacetanilide and Derivatives as Secondary Ligands

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Manuscript received 20 October 1978, revised 31 March 1979, accepted 6 June 1979

Mixed ligand complexes of the type $[CuLL']$, where LH=salicylaldehyde or 2-OH-acetophenoneimine and L'H=acetoacetanilide or derivatives have been synthesised. These complexes undergo amine exchange over the Schiff base on treatment with methylamine, ethylamine and ethanolamine. The complexes have been characterised by elemental analyses, TLC, conductance, magnetic moment and spectral studies,

FOLLOWING our earlier studies¹⁻³ on mixed ligand complexes of the type $[MLL']$, where M=Cu(II) or Ni(II); L=salicylaldehyde or 2-OH-acetophenone and L'= β -diketone, β -Ketoanilides having the similar O-O donor sites and pseudoaromaticity in the chelate ring as β -diketones have been utilised as the secondary ligands.

In this paper, complexes of the type $[CuLL']$, where LH=salicylaldehyde or 2-OH-acetophenone and L'H=acetoacetanilide or acetoacet-*o*-toluidide or acetoacet-*o*-anisidide have been reported. An attempt has been made to study the extent of π -interaction in the β -ketoanilide complexes.

Materials and Method :

2-Hydroxyacetophenone was prepared by Fries migration of phenyl acetate using anhydrous aluminium chloride without solvent and was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Other chemicals used were of BDH/Fluka.

Preparation of mixed imine Schiff base complexes(I) :

To the solution of copper acetate in excess ammonia was added an alcoholic solution of the two ligands, in equimolar ratio. The mixture was stirred well and the solid that separated was filtered, washed in turn with water and 50% alcohol. The compound was recrystallised from chloroform and analysed. (In the case where 2-hydroxyacetophenone was the primary ligand, it required refluxing.)

Preparation of N-alkylamine compounds(II) :

The compounds were prepared by amine exchange method. Complex I was treated with

very dilute amines (methyl or ethyl) $\sim 0.05M$ (3-5 ml) and was refluxed for some time. The solids were recovered and recrystallised as before.

Preparation of compound(III) :

(I) was refluxed on a water bath with an ethanolic solution of ethanolamine. The solid that separated on adding water to the reaction mixture was filtered, washed with water and 50% ethanol and recrystallised from ethanol.

Results and Discussion

It is seen that the aldehyde or 2-hydroxyacetophenone part undergoes Schiff base formation. The β -ketoanilides, however, remain unaffected. This may be attributed to the fact that like the β -diketones, the β -ketoanilides also form a six-membered ring on coordination with delocalised π electrons over it which gives it a pseudoaromatic character and stability.⁴ As a result of this the reactivity of the carbonyl group is reduced and no Schiff base formation takes place in the β -ketoanilide part of the molecule.

The amine exchange reaction proceeds by a nucleophilic attack of the exchanging amine on the electron deficient carbon of the polarised imine. A more basic and hence a more nucleophilic amine replaces a less basic amine from the Schiff base. The reaction is, however, concentration dependent also. A higher concentration of less basic amine may replace the more basic amine from the Schiff base^{5,6}. Amine exchange was carried out using excess amine and employing amine as the reaction solvent. In the amine exchange reaction with ethanolamine the aldimine part reacted with ethanolamine to form a tridentate ligand, in which OH

- I R=H or CH₃ or OCH₃,
R'=H or CH₃.
- II R=H or CH₃ or OCH₃,
R'=H or CH₃,
R''=CH₃ or C₂H₅.
- III R'=H or CH₃.

group of ethanolamine provided the third coordination site. The anilide part was, however, removed and the final compound(III) attained tetracoordination through coordination of a water molecule.

Similar monomeric complexes of tridentate

ligands with solvent molecule occupying the fourth position have been reported earlier⁷. Reaction of ethanolamine with bis(salicylaldiminato) Cu(II) have been carried out in our laboratory⁸. It has been observed that one of the salicylaldehyde molecule forms a tridentate ligand with monoethanolamine and occupies three positions around the Cu(II) ion ; the other salicylaldehyde molecule is removed.

TLC analysis shows the compounds to be pure. The results of elemental analysis agree with the suggested structures. All the Schiff base complexes obtained are soluble in common organic solvents. They are found to be non-conducting indicating their non-electrolytic nature.

The Cu(II) complexes are paramagnetic having magnetic moments corresponding to one unpaired electron. The visible spectrum shows a broad band ~ 580 nm in agreement with square planar structure.

In compound I (R''=H) the band at ~1600 cm⁻¹ corresponds to ν_{C=N} of the imine linkage. There is also a band at ~3300 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν_{N-H} stretching frequency. This band is, however, absent in case of Schiff base complexes derived from alkylamines (Comp. II. R''=CH₃ or C₂H₅).

The IR spectrum of compound(III) exhibits a broad band in the region ~3400 cm⁻¹ corresponding to OH stretch, confirming the presence of water. There is also a band around ~800 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the O-H out of plane deformation. This indicates the presence of coordinated water and confirms a square planar structure for compound III. Thus, the tridentate ligand occupies three positions around the copper atom, the fourth being occupied by a water molecule.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, VISIBLE SPECTRAL DATA AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF THE MIXED LIGAND SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES OF Cu(II)

Complex	% of Metal		% of Nitrogen		λ _{max} (nm)	#B.M.
	Calculated	Found	Calculated	Found		
Ia (salicylideneaminato-acetoacetanilidato) Cu(II)	17.67	17.50	7.79	7.76	580	1.88
Ib (salicylideneaminato-acetoacet- <i>o</i> -toluididato) Cu(II)	17.01	16.67	7.50	8.10	580	1.91
Ic (salicylideneaminato- <i>o</i> -acetoacet- <i>o</i> -anisididato) Cu(II)	16.81	16.00	7.19	7.50	580	1.95
Id (2-OH-acetophenoniminato-acetoacet-anilidato) Cu(II)	17.01	16.96	7.50	7.55	600	1.86
Ie (2-OH-acetophenoniminato-acetoacet- <i>o</i> -toluididato) Cu(II)	16.40	16.51	7.28	7.14	560	1.89
If (2-O-1-acetophenoniminato-acetoacet- <i>o</i> -anisididato) Cu(II)	15.75	15.60	6.94	7.17	600	1.74
IIa (N-Methyl salicylideneaminato-acetoacetanilidato) Cu(II)	17.01	16.67	7.50	7.12	610	1.91
IIb (N-Methyl salicylideneaminato-acetoacet- <i>o</i> -toluididato) Cu(II)	16.99	16.52	7.23	7.00	580	1.97
IIc (N-Methyl salicylideneaminato-acetoacet- <i>o</i> -anisididato) Cu(II)	15.75	15.52	6.94	7.23	580	1.86
IId (N-Ethyl salicylideneaminato-acetoacetanilidato) Cu(II)	16.95	16.12	7.21	6.72	580	1.98
IIe (N-Ethyl salicylideneaminato-acetoacet- <i>o</i> -toluididato) Cu(II)	15.82	15.59	6.97	7.70	580	1.92
IIf (N-Ethyl salicylideneaminatoacet- <i>o</i> -anisididato) Cu(II)	15.22	15.48	6.71	6.97	580	1.82
IIIa (N-Hydroxyethyl salicylideneaminato) Cu(II). H ₂ O	25.88	25.57	5.72	5.85	600	1.75
IIIb (N-Hydroxyethyl-(1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)ethylideneaminato) Cu(II). H ₂ O	24.48	24.37	5.89	5.08	620	1.72

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. K. N. Trivedi, Head, Department of Chemistry, M. S. University of Baroda, Baroda-2, for providing necessary laboratory facilities. Our thanks are also due to the University Grants Commission and the CSIR for providing fellowship to (GK) and (UC).

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